

**IMPROVEMENT PLAN ON THE UTILIZATION OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS
WITH TECHNOLOGY-ENHANCED ASSESSMENT (TEA) TOOL**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Information and Communications Technology (ICT) has transformed the traditional classroom into an innovative educational resource. It has converted everybody's needs to electronic forms and recently the general paper-pen tests/exams into an electronic assessment. Hence, investigating the utilization of mobile applications with technology-enhanced assessment (TEA) tool can help teachers enhance their knowledge and skills in using technology for classroom assessment.

Methods: The researcher employed the descriptive research design and Input-Process-Output (IPO) approach in developing the TEA tool. Frequency count, percentage, and weighted mean was used to analyze and interpret the gathered data. The study involved 116 Grade 5 teachers in the East Unit of the SDO of Ilocos Norte.

Results: Study revealed that most teachers have already earned units in their master's degree, have taught for ten (10) years, and have participated in local trainings related to ICT, assessment, content, and classroom management. Among the ten (10) identified available mobile applications with TEA tool, teachers sometimes use the Kahoot It, Google Quiz, Plickers, and Quizziz and they never utilized Quizalize, Socratives, Poll Everywhere, Quizlet, Padlet, and Edmodo. As to teachers' level of proficiency in the use of mobile applications, most of them are at the Entry Level. The respondents agreed that they encountered the issues and concerns under accessibility, usability, and connectivity.

Conclusions: The improvement plan on the utilization of mobile applications with TEA Tool is found very highly valid in addressing teachers' issues and concerns. Hence, it is recommended for possible adoption to help teachers develop their skills in using ICT for classroom assessment.

Keywords: Utilization, Mobile Applications, Technology-Enhanced Assessment (TEA) Tool, Improvement Plan

Introduction

Information technology has transformed the classroom into a great educational resource. E-books, e-learning, e-mail, e-banking, e-bay, and e-games have become everyone's requirements. According to Trillo, et al. (2017), e-learning has become a complement to face-to-face classes, which pushes the advent of electronic assessment to replace paper-pen tests/exams. JISC defines e-assessment as technology-enhanced assessment (2006; cited in Appiah & Van, 2018).

Elmahdi et al., (2016) mentioned that mobile applications help teachers effectively and efficiently assess students' knowledge, concepts, and skills by providing user-friendly technology since teachers only need in their classroom a cell phone, or tablet in e-assessment. Similarly, McCain (2019) mentioned that mobile applications help overcome educational problems. Interactive and personalized learning are the assets that students get from mobile apps. Education-based apps provide convenience by helping students to realize more in less time.

According to My Edvisor (2020), mobile apps can be students' best friend in times of need and can build harmonious relationships among teachers, learners, and parents. Based on the research of Ayres, Mechling, and Sansosti (2013), the growing number of studies investigating the utilization of technology-based interventions and mobile technologies shows the importance of technology to support students in education. Most research studies center on determining the relationship of assessing students' cognitive skills to their academic achievement.

The integration of information technology has transformed the classroom into a valuable educational resource. The widespread use of technology, such as e-learning, e-books, e-mail, e-banking, e-bay, and e-games, has made technology a necessity in education. E-learning has become a complement to traditional face-to-face classes, leading to the development of technology-enhanced assessment methods to replace traditional paper-pen exams (Trillo et al., 2007; Usta & Ullman, 2016). Mobile applications have been shown to be effective tools for teachers to assess student knowledge, concepts, and skills (Elmahdi, Al-Hattami, & Fwzi, 2016; McCain, 2019). These apps provide interactive and personalized learning experiences for students and offer convenience by helping them achieve more in less time (My Edvisor, 2020). The growing body of research investigating the use of technology-based interventions and mobile technologies in education highlights the importance of technology in supporting student learning and development (Ayres, Mechling, & Sansosti, 2013). Many studies focus on the relationship between students' cognitive skills and academic achievement, highlighting the potential for technology to positively impact student success.

Thus, the objective of this study was to create a plan for enhancing the use of mobile applications with technology-enhanced assessment (TEA) tools. specifically to determine the characteristics of the teachers, identify the available mobile applications with technology-enhanced assessment (TEA) tools, assess the level of usage of mobile applications among teachers, evaluate the competence of teachers in using mobile applications with technology-enhanced assessment (TEA) tools, and identify the challenges and concerns of teachers in using mobile applications.

Research Questions

The study aimed to develop an improvement plan on the utilization of mobile applications with technology-enhanced assessment (TEA) tool. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions: (1) to determine the profile of teachers; (2) to identify the

available mobile applications with technology-enhanced assessment (TEA) tool; (3) to determine the utilization level of mobile applications among teachers; (4) to assess the level of proficiency of teachers in the utilization of mobile applications with technology-enhanced assessment (TEA) tool; and (5) to determine the issues and concerns of teachers in the utilization of mobile applications.

Methods

A descriptive research design and IPO (Input, Process, and Output) Approach was utilized in this study. The researcher utilized a total enumeration which involved 116 grade 5 teachers from the different schools in the East Unit of the Schools Division of Ilocos Norte.

The researcher used two questionnaires to gather data. The first questionnaire was used to collect data and consisted of four parts: (1) respondents' profile, (2) available mobile applications with TEA tool, (3) teachers' level of proficiency in the utilization of mobile applications with the TEA tool, and (4) issues and concerns in the utilization of mobile applications with the TEA tool.

The second questionnaire was a content validation instrument in the form of a rating scale patterned from the Evaluation Sheet on School Improvement Plan (SIP) of SDO-IN. After retrieving the data, statistical procedure followed, frequency count, percentage, and weighted mean was used to analyze and interpret the gathered data.

Results and Discussion

Part 1. Profile of Teachers

Table 1. Profile of Grade 5 Teachers in the East Unit (n=116)

Variable	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree holder	14	12.10
Bachelor's Degree with MA Units	100	86.20
Master's Degree	2	1.70
Years of Teaching		
0-3	14	12.10
4-6	27	23.30
7-9	21	18.10
10 and above	54	46.60
Training/Seminars		
ICT/Technical Skills		
School/District Level	60	51.70
Division Level	40	34.50
Regional Level	2	1.70
National Level	7	6.00
None	7	6.00
Assessment/ Evaluation		
School/District Level	58	50.00
Division Level	38	32.80
National Level	2	1.70
None	18	15.50
Subject/Content		
School/District Level	56	48.30
Division Level	43	37.10
Regional Level	3	2.60
National Level	2	1.70
None	12	10.30

Classroom Management		
School/District Level	74	63.80
Division Level	23	19.80
Regional Level	3	2.60
National Level	2	1.70
None	14	12.10

Table 1 presents the profile of teachers, specifically on their educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and training or seminars related to ICT or technical skill development, assessment/evaluation concepts and applications in the classroom, mastering subjects/content in the different learning areas, and classroom management.

In terms of educational attainment, Table 1 shows that 100 or 86.20% of the respondents has earned units in their master's degree, 14 or 12.10% of them are bachelor's degree holders, while two or 1.70% of the respondents are master's degree holders. On the other hand, none of the respondents have units at the doctorate level and doctorate graduate. The results imply that teachers pursue graduate studies to enhance their potentials and acquire new skills. Likewise, through continuous education, teachers can develop their communication and social skills because they meet people who have different backgrounds. Hence, they get to meet successful professionals.

Similarly, the table shows that majority of the teachers (54 or 46.60%) have been in the profession for ten (10) years or more and have gained enough knowledge and skills in the teaching profession. Twenty-seven or 23.30% of them have served for four to six years. Meanwhile, 21 or 18.10% of them have taught for seven to nine years, while 14 or 12.10% have been in the teaching service for zero to three years. The data suggest that there is a big number of beginners in the profession; therefore, needs support in terms of training and enhancement programs.

This study divides trainings and seminars into four categories: ICT/Technical Skills, Assessment/Evaluation, Subject/Content, and Classroom Management. The chart shows that 60 or 51.70% of respondents participated in school or district-level ICT training, while just two or 1.70% participated at the regional level. The data suggest that provincial instructors rarely attend regional, national, or worldwide seminars. Only a few DepEd seminars are free, and most are invitational or run by commercial organizations. Due to time constraints, school duties, and money constraints, Gonong (2014) states that instructors rarely attend training or seminars. To adapt to educational innovations, especially ICT reforms, teachers require more rigorous training or seminars.

As to trainings or seminars related to Assessment/Evaluation, data reveals that out of the 116 respondents, 58 or 50% have undergone school or district training on assessment/evaluation. On the other hand, 38 or 32.80% have division-level training. Meanwhile, 18 or 15.50% have no training, while only two or 1.70% have national-level training or seminars. The findings suggest that half of the total number of respondents have training or seminars related to assessment or evaluation at the school or district level only. According to Flow of Thoughts (n.d.), assessment is vital for the improvement of learning and suggests that teachers need training and support to enable them to make valuable assessment decisions, to provide quality feedback to learners, and to teach learners to receive feedback positively and use the information contained within it effectively to improve their work.

In terms of subject area or content, data show that 56 or 48.30% of the teachers have training or seminars at the school or district level. On the other hand, 43 or 37.10% have training or seminar at the division level, while there are 12 or 10.30% do not have any training related to subject area or content. Three or 2.60% of the teachers have training at the regional level, while only two or 1.70% of them have training at the national level. Kamamia, et al. (2014) stress that through the mastery of subject matter, teachers can impart the right skills of communication, collaboration, critical thinking, and creativity based on the three learning

domains: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor and suggest that teachers need to master the contents of the different learning areas they taught by attending various seminars or training, which can help them achieve mastery and proficiency of the core contents of the subject.

Regarding classroom management, most of the respondents (74 or 63.80%) had received training or seminars at the school or district level. 23 respondents (19.80%) received division-level training, while 14 respondents (12.10%) had no training. Only 3 respondents (2.60%) received regional training, and 2 respondents (1.70%) received training or seminars at the national level. As stated by Marzano et al. (2003), teachers play multiple roles in the classroom, with one of the most important being as a classroom manager. According to Marzano et al. (2003), a well-managed classroom provides an environment where teaching and learning can flourish. They also note that creating a well-managed classroom takes significant effort and does not happen spontaneously.

Among the four categories of training or seminars, teachers participate the most in training or seminars on classroom management. This implies that teachers want to equip themselves with skills and techniques that they can employ to keep students organized, orderly, focused, attentive, on task, and academically productive during a class (Great School Partnership, 2021).

Mobile Applications with Technology-Enhanced Assessment (TEA) Tool. The use of digital technology, specifically mobile applications, in education has attracted much interest in recent years. Mobile applications are a fundamental feature of mobile devices, and the volume and complexity of apps continue to increase unabated. These features include being interactive, motivational, autonomous. Likewise, mobile applications provide immediate feedback, review, retention, engagement, and practical applications to current and future learning experiences. Some of this available mobile application with technology-enhanced assessment (TEA) tool includes *Kahoot It!*, *Google Quiz*, *Plickers*, *Quizziz*, *Quizalize*, *Socratives*, *Poll Everywhere*, *Quizlet*, *Padlet*, and *Edmodo*.

Utilization Level of Mobile Applications with Technology-Enhanced Assessment (TEA) of Teachers

Table 2. Utilization Level of Mobile Applications with Technology-Enhanced Assessment (TEA) Tool of Teachers (n=116)

List of Mobile Applications	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Quizalize	1.28	Never Utilized
Quiziz	1.54	Sometimes Utilized
Plickers	1.72	Sometimes Utilized
Socrative	1.21	Never Utilized
Poll Everywhere	1.32	Never Utilized
Kahoot It!	1.90	Sometimes Utilized
Google Form (Quiz)	1.86	Sometimes Utilized
Quizlet	1.37	Never Utilized
Padlet	1.20	Never Utilized
Edmodo	1.23	Never Utilized

Legend:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
3.51-4.00	Always Utilized
2.51-3.50	Often Utilized
1.51-2.50	Sometimes Utilized
1.00-1.50	Never Utilized

Data shows that teachers sometimes utilized four out of the ten free mobile applications in assessing their learners' knowledge and skills. The table shows that *Kahoot It!*, an application that promotes both individualized and team collaborative assessment, obtained the highest mean (1.90). On the other hand, *Google Form (Quiz)*, a survey and polling software,

obtained a mean of 1.86; *Plickers*, a mobile application that uses *QR Codes*, has a mean of 1.72; and *Quiziz*, an application similar to Kahoot, got a mean of 1.54. According to Clark and Mayer (2008, cited in Plump, et al.,2017), the benefits gained from using new technologies will depend on the extent to which they are used in ways compatible with the learning process. In the case of Kahoot, they state that using it can support student metacognition by providing immediate feedback. He also pointed out that *Kahoot* supports the construction of new knowledge and understanding by providing explanations during or after the game.

Meanwhile, six out of ten free mobile applications with TEA tool were never utilized. Padlet, a virtual bulletin board where learners can post their answers, registered the lowest mean (1.20). *Quizalize*, a gamified-based platform, obtained a mean of 1.28, while *Socrative*, an application allowing the teacher to create true/false-based questions, got a mean of 1.21. *Edmodo*, a learning management system including the construction of formative assessment, has a mean of 1.23, while *Poll Everywhere*, an application gathering learner’s responses through polls, has a mean of 1.32. Finally, *Quizlet*, a similar application to *Kahoot* and *Quizzes*, has a mean of 1.37. Weller (2013, cited in Kleinsmith, 2017) investigated the effects of using *Padlet* at the elementary level. It appears promising that *Padlet* may serve as a tool that can be easily incorporated into any classroom, specifically at-risk students receiving remediation.

In general, these mobile applications are classified as free applications. It means that these are free of charge and are readily available to download in *Apple Store* and *Playstore* via smartphones or tablets. In this study, the researcher discovered that teachers are only starting to use these mobile applications with the technology-enhanced assessment (TEA) tool in their classroom.

Level of Proficiency of Teachers in the Utilization of Mobile Applications with Technology-Enhanced Assessment (TEA) Tool

Table 3. Level of Proficiency of Teachers in the Utilization of Mobile Applications with Technology-Enhanced Assessment (TEA) Tool (n=116)

Level of Utilization	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Entry	46	39.70
Adoption	39	33.60
Adaptation	21	18.10
Appropriation	5	4.30
Innovation	5	4.30
Total	116	100

Table 3 reveals that most of the respondents are at the Entry Level (Level 1), which means that 46 teachers (39.70%) know the basics of using mobile applications. Based on the ACOT Model, teachers at this level tend to have a little discomfort with the use of technology and rely on the technical help of others. At this level, teachers typically use mobile applications in group activities. The big number of teachers at the Entry Level means that teachers have limited experience using mobile applications with technology-enhanced assessment tool. This is because most of them have only trainings or seminars on ICT at the school or district level. Hence, these seminars are not adequate to enhance their technical and assessment skills.

The table also shows that 39 (33.60%) of the respondents are at the “Adoption” Level (Level 2), which means that they have a higher level of utilization of mobile applications with the technology-enhanced assessment tool. The results imply that those teachers have already started and adopted using mobile applications in assessing their learners. Meanwhile, 21 or 18.10% of respondents are at the “Adaptation” Level (Level 3), at this level, teachers figure out ways to use the devices to their advantage in teaching like finding new ways of monitoring student work, grading tests, creating new materials, and tailoring skills to each student. Lastly,

five or 4.30% of the respondents belong to the two highest levels: “Appropriation” (Level 4) and “Innovation” (Level 5).

At the Appropriation level, teachers tend to make a traditional classroom into a student-centered learning environment, which uses technology and promotes cooperative and interdisciplinary works. Teachers who are at this level have shifted their attitudes toward using technology in the classroom. Moreover, according to Cuban (2016), teachers, who are at the Innovation level, often use mobile applications to create or design authentic task or assessment which they employ new ways of teaching like project-based learning, team teaching, and individualized lessons.

Issues and Concerns in the Utilization of Mobile Applications with Technology-Enhanced Assessment (TEA) Tool

Table 4. Issues and Concerns on the Utilization of Mobile Applications

Issues and Concerns	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
A. Accessibility	3.41	Agree
1. It helps teachers to give a realistic picture of the task to the learners.	3.09	Agree
2. It is better than printed material in presenting a certain task to the learner.	3.14	Agree
3. It accommodates learner with disabilities through multimedia inputs which cannot be provided in the traditional assessment.	3.30	Agree
4. It allows pupils to share their insights through input mechanism such as a chatbox	3.16	Agree
5. It requires high skills in exploring and navigating all the content of the task.	3.22	Agree
Composite Mean	3.22	Agree
B. Usability		
1. It improves student efficiency in accomplishing a task in a given period.	3.16	Agree
2. It provides an opportunity for teachers to present tasks interactively which improves learners' engagement.	3.30	Agree
3. It provides satisfaction among learners while using it in accomplishing a certain task than the traditional assessments.	3.18	Agree
4. It helps a teacher to gather accurate data on learners' achievement for its data analytical feature than manual checking and scoring	3.28	Agree
5. It helps a teacher to score or mark learners accomplished task in a short period and can provide immediate feedback	3.37	Agree
Composite Mean	3.26	Agree
C. Connectivity/Availability		
1. It is effective when there are sufficient available devices for all the learners since it is for individualized learning only.	3.43	Agree
2. It is only effective when there is fast and sustained internet access.	3.58	Strongly Agree
3. It needs technical skills in implementing assessment using mobile applications	3.43	Agree
4. It provides discomfort on learners who have a low awareness and of how to use a mobile application	3.24	Agree
5. It requires the availability of the latest devices in the market	3.17	Agree
Composite Mean	3.37	Agree
Overall Mean	3.28	Agree

Legend:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
3.51-4.00	Strongly Agree
2.51-3.50	Agree
1.51-2.50	Disagree
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree

The data in the table reveals that the composite mean score is 3.22, indicating that the respondents generally agree that they experience all the issues and concerns related to accessibility. The item "it helps teachers to give a realistic picture of the task to the learners" received the highest mean score of 3.41, indicating that mobile applications use multimedia elements such as images, audio, videos, etc. to engage and interest learners. On the other hand, the item "it is better than printed material in presenting a certain task to the learner" had the

lowest mean score of 3.09, indicating that technology does not completely replace traditional methods of instruction and assessment, but rather it supports and enhances the quality of instruction and assessment.

In terms of usability with a composite mean of 3.26, it suggests that the respondents agree that they encounter all the presented issues and concerns. The item, “it helps a teacher to score or mark learners’ accomplished task in a short period and can provide immediate feedback” obtained the highest mean (3.38). According to Nielsen (1993, cited in Dourado & Canedo, 2018), one important component of mobile applications is their usability features like efficiency, effectiveness, and satisfaction. On the other hand, the item, “it improves student efficiency in accomplishing a task in each period”, got the lowest mean (3.16). Technology helps learners accomplish certain tasks because it gives more resources and information about a problem. However, it does not guarantee learner’s efficiency because there are other factors like knowledge and skills that contribute to the learner’s performance.

As to Connectivity/Availability, the table shows that the composite mean, 3.37, suggests that the respondents agree that they encounter all the presented issues and concerns under connectivity or availability. The item, “it is only effective when there is fast and sustained internet access”, got the highest mean (3.58). Meanwhile, the item, “it requires the availability of the latest devices in the market”, obtained the lowest mean (3.17). This means that teachers can only use these mobile applications successfully if consideration is given to the availability of devices with good specifications. According to Quareshi, et al. (2012, cited in Kanwal & Rehman, 2017), technology innovation comes with challenges in the implementation of the said project or program. Some of these challenges are technical difficulties and access to computers/mobile devices. include installation, availability of latest technology, fast internet connection, and uninterrupted supply of electricity, maintenance, administration, security, and absence of technical support.

The overall mean, 3.28, suggests that the respondents agree that they encounter all the presented issues and concerns under accessibility, usability, and connectivity/availability. It is essential to know the issues and problems that confront teachers to implement appropriate interventions that can improve the educational perspectives of using mobile applications to support and deliver the assessment.

Summary on the Issues and Concerns in the Utilization of Mobile Applications

Table 5. Summary on the Issues and Concerns on the Utilization of Mobile Applications

Issues and Concerns	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Accessibility	3.22	Agree
Usability	3.26	Agree
Connectivity/Availability	3.37	Agree
Overall Mean	3.28	Agree

Legend:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
3.51-4.00	Strongly Agree
2.51-3.50	Agree
1.51-2.50	Disagree
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree

The overall mean, 3.28, suggests that the respondents *agree* that they encounter all the presented issues and concerns under accessibility, usability, and connectivity/availability. Thus, it is important to solve these issues and concerns by providing enough funds for additional resources like tablets and smartphones, enhancing and securing strong and fast internet connectivity, and implementing skills development programs and training for teachers.

Conclusion

In the light of the findings, the researcher presents the following conclusions: In terms of the teachers' level of proficiency in the utilization of mobile applications with TEA tool, majority of the teacher-respondents are still at the three lowest levels: Entry, Adoption, and Adaptation Levels. Only four out of the 10 mobile applications with the TEA tool are sometimes utilized. In addition, there are issues and concerns that challenge them in the implementation and integration of the mobile applications with TEA tool into their classroom assessment. Thus, the researcher developed the Improvement Plan on the Utilization of Mobile Applications with Technology-Enhanced Assessment (TEA) tool that seeks to address teachers' issues and concerns and increase their skills in using mobile applications with TEA tool for classroom assessment.

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